

PLANINNG AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES

PEARLS

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Abstract:

According to Work Package 3, this deliverable presents the first version of the participatory methodology. This methodology includes the results of the research carried out in the different secondments carried out as well as CLANER's own experience in this type of actions and others that are considered of interest for this project.

Index:

1. Techniques and instruments of participation.....	5
1.1. Interview techniques	5
1.2. Questionnaire techniques	6
1.3. Techniques for participation in discussion groups/Focus Group, collective intelligence sessions and conference.....	7
2. Identification and selection of key actors	8
3. PEARLS Consortium.....	10

1. Techniques and instruments of participation

The instrumentalization of a participatory and open work scenario around the development of renewable energy projects and the conservation of the landscape of the territory is articulated on five types of participation techniques such as: personal interviews, participatory questionnaires and face-to-face or online discussion groups (depending on the progress of the global pandemic situation caused by COVID-19), Participatory days and online voting. The application of the techniques will be based on the design and development of the following instruments.

1.1. Interview techniques

Interviews	
Objective	The interviews will serve to determine and agree on the scope and objectives to be pursued by the participatory process of the project linked to renewable energies.
Procedure	They will be developed through a pre-designed script or thematic scheme (mixed or semi-structured), although with flexibility for the inclusion of questions that may be useful for the purposes of each specific content to be developed in the study. The interviews will be proposed in advance, and the interviewees will be informed of the objective of the study and the session, the duration and the use that will be made of the information.
Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of the interview script. • Selection of people to interview. • Arrangement of interviews. • Conducting interviews. • Analysis of the responses. • Drawing conclusions.
Representatives of recipient entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management staff of the public institutions of the territory and the promoter company • Associative fabric (associations, federations, other representative entities). • Business fabric (associations and representative entities of each motor sector). • Field of knowledge (University).

1.2. Questionnaire techniques

Questionario	
Objectives	The online questionnaires will serve to qualify the findings resulting from the recorded data and other information generation tools, but with a much more sectoral scope depending on the actions to be carried out in the areas of implementation, etc.
Procedure	The main method of capturing answers will be done through a google docs that allows answering questionnaires quickly and comfortably through fixed and mobile devices. It will be direct access through the online platform and will be sent reinforcement via mailing.
Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire design. • Sending the questionnaire link. • Monitoring and control of responses. • Telephone contact to resolve doubts and facilitate the completion of the questionnaire. • Quality control. • Analysis of responses. • Drawing conclusions.
Target entities	The different entities linked to environmental actions or with influence on the environment as well as citizens in general. Different questionnaires will be developed depending on the type of recipient entity.

1.3. Techniques for participation in discussion groups/Focus Group, collective intelligence sessions and conference.

Focus Groups	
Objectives	Like the interviews, they will serve to qualify the findings resulting from the recorded data and the other information generation tools, but they will have a much more sectoral scope than the interviews and will be worked on territorially depending on the result of the analysis of the draft renewable energy implementation project, as well as the diagnosis of the situation of the territory in terms of landscape conservation. Discussion groups will also be created with representatives of different public and private entities, territorial management and knowledge, as well as citizens in general.
Procedure SWOT/ETPO or CMEA analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These techniques will be used to identify the strengths, weaknesses, successes and setbacks of actions at territorial level linked to environmental management and the implementation of renewable energies. In a complementary way, these techniques will also identify the threats opportunities, potentialities and obstacles for their improvement. • They will also be applied to the objective of identifying the challenges for each of the social groups and public and private entities, the needs of the territory and citizens and to identify opportunities in terms of cooperation for the implementation of the project. • Cooperation should be constituted as a solution or a real added value for its own public administration.
Tasks	<p>Preparation of the session:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of the roadmap of the session to be agreed with the project management. • Preparation of the invitation mail model + the agenda of the session. • Preparation of online registration questionnaire to send with the invitation email.. <p>Post-debate: evaluation and monitoring:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of a report of results of each session to send to the participants and include their subsequent contributions. • Preparation of a satisfaction survey for each session.
Target entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus Group: environmental experts on landscape and renewable energies and the different subjects involved in the development of a project of this type. • Collective intelligence sessions: internal project implementation managers • Conferences: general city and civil society.

2. Identification and selection of key actors

A determining aspect of the success of a participatory process is to have the collaboration of key actors and citizens. To do this, the identification of actors must take into account three basic principles:

Multilevel. The participation model must interact with society avoiding social hierarchy, with the participation of all people who want to express their opinion. The barrier between key agents (administration, public and private entities...) and citizens must be broken, so that both agents position themselves at the same level when building a sustainable territory model.

Multisectoral. It must have the participation of all sectors of the population to be able to incorporate different points of view that enrich the debate and provide new ideas that can be implemented through actions to expand social benefit and achieve the objectives set more quickly.

With co-responsibility. It must be a vehicle instrument that incorporates the vision of coresponsibility that is needed for the implementation of renewable energies by citizens. At the same time, this must be avoided from negatively affecting the implementation of the future project, establishing coordinators whose function is to promote and streamline processes.

The **criteria** to be applied for the selection of persons representing the types of agents mentioned above are the following:

- Numerical representativeness: number of associates
- Territorial representativeness: territory where it exercises its activity or competence
- Relevance: key role it has in the process (institutional, business, etc.)
- Suitability: link with environmental management
- Interest: show of interest in participating in the process
- Potential communicator: role it has as a channel of communication and dissemination in its environment

In the case of online participation activities, these will be open to as many agents as possible both internally, as well as external to the public.

In this case, PERALS proposes an initial list of types of actors based on the following groups of agents for each of the discussion groups:

- **Institutional managers:** with an impact on the elaboration and subsequent implementation of the project: managers and staff of public administrations and of interest and linked to environmental management.
- **Social and economic representatives:** neighborhood associations, environmental organizations, school associations of mothers and fathers, associations of merchants and entrepreneurs, agricultural cooperatives, representatives of the tourism sector, other organized social groups, etc.
- **Educational community:** representatives of educational centers (schools, institutes).
- **Opinion generators:** media with greater local incidence.
- **Citizenship in general:** who wants to participate individually and not under the representation of any specific group

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